

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MODERN INNOVATIONS IN EDUCATIONAL SPHERE

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Abstract

This article addresses the issues of modern innovations, which aim to form a new type of higher education in the 21st century. Such innovations are often called "breakthrough", as they break the status quo, changing education and its established stereotypes. In addition, the notion of breakthrough innovations is revealed, a mini-review of the most relevant innovations, especially such phenomena as online education and mass open online courses, and an analytical review of the potential impact of breakthrough innovations on Ukrainian higher education is given.

Keywords: breakthrough innovations, online education, massive open online courses, online course movement, information technology electronic open badges

The field of education has long been marginalized from radical innovation changes and remains a traditional sphere based on its origins dating back to antiquity. Despite this, the importance of innovation cannot be underestimated. A simple device such as the chalkboard, introduced at the dawn of the nineteenth century, is still used in schools and prestigious universities. And what would the world and the education system be like without Gutenberg's invention of book printing? Today, the right question arises: can the Internet and information technology have a similar impact on education as book printing?

The idea of breakthrough innovation is most often associated with the name of Harvard University scientist Clayton Christensen, who formulated it in the mid-1990s in his book "Innovator's Dilemma" [1]. Breakthrough innovation is an innovative product that initially has a lower quality in relation to a traditionally offered product. Such a product is usually cheaper and more accessible to a wide range of customers and over time displaces the traditional product from the market. Christensen uses dozens of examples to illustrate breakthrough innovation, but consider just a few. As an example, the simplest is postal services. Many readers probably can't remember the last time they went to the post office to send a letter. After all, e-mail is much faster, easier and more reliable. Moreover, young readers may not even use email, but send photos, audio, video and text messages via one of the popular cell phone applications. The example of digital photography is an interesting one. It is ironic, but it is a fact that at one time the absolute leader of film photography, Kodak, was the first to develop an innovative digital photo. However, failing to see the potential of this invention, the company handed it over to an outside organization and a decade later found itself on the verge of bankruptcy from its own breakthrough innovation. Note that digital photography was initially inferior to traditional photography in terms of image quality and the existing digital memory capacity at the time could

only hold a few images. However, the capacity of computer memory, according to Moore's Law [2], was doubled in an 18-month period. This changed the entire photography industry in a matter of years.

Among the breakthrough innovations in education today are such active and rapidly developing forms of learning as online education and massive open online courses (MOOCs).

Online education as a phenomenon is not new, but has gained the greatest development in the last decade. It is at the current stage that online education has established itself as a legitimate and employer-recognized form of higher education. Today, there are highly profitable and sustainable organizational models that provide a comparable academic experience in terms of content and requirements due to the unprecedented development of technology.

Massive open online courses (MOOCs). This is a new and most discussed phenomenon among practitioners and researchers. These courses are relatively new, but the number of learners is already in the millions. Being absolutely free and available in almost any country in the world, MOOCs have become a great help for people who are improving their skills and striving for knowledge. Competency-based learning. It should be noted here that we are talking about competency-based education and not the concept itself. Curriculum in this model is broken down into clear competencies that a student acquires regardless of the number of academic hours or practical training. In this approach there are no assessments, practically a student can receive a diploma in the shortest possible time if he/she demonstrates all the required competencies. Open educational resources. The best known example of such resources is Khan's Academy. They are often used as an "aid" by teachers in English-speaking schools. These resources vary in terms of technology, specialization and other parameters, but have in common that they are free and open to all (both teachers and students). A big ad-

vantage is that electronic resources are constantly updated, often using video and interactive methods to present the material. The flipped classroom is a pedagogical approach in which the standard elements of passive (lectures) and active (assignments, cases, projects, discussions, group work) learning are interchanged. That is, students are given a video lecture as a homework assignment, and in the classroom the students have to consolidate their knowledge. This allows for better learning outcomes and deeper student engagement in the learning process.

The movement of electronic open badges does not have a particularly high "breakthrough" potential to impact education, but as a tool for lifelong learning and professional development, electronic badges are already widely used. In essence, badges are visual evidence of attaining a certain level of mastery in a particular competency. Tens of thousands of badges are available today, and leading this movement is the Mozilla Open Badges Initiative. Different researchers point to other breakthrough innovations, but this list includes the most common concepts. Undoubtedly, each of the innovations deserves close attention, but the focus is on online learning and massive open online (MOOC) courses.

Today, we are not talking about online education as an unusual phenomenon. During the pandemic, much of education has shifted to an online format. As recently as 2013, the Sloan Consortium estimated that one in three U.S. college students took at least one course online; other data puts the figure at 41.7%. Such data is strong evidence of the ubiquity, effectiveness, and accessibility of online education, as well as its high integration into the classroom. The online education industry has experienced a real boom - as of 2019. The attention to online education is also high among traditional universities - two-thirds of U.S. university leaders say that online education is a key priority for their institution, and nine out of ten universities believe that its quality will improve along with increasing student enrollment.

Online education opens access to universities for people with disabilities, the working population, rural youth, and other segments of the population that have traditionally lacked extensive opportunities for higher education. Aligning learning with work has the obvious advantage of integrating practice and learning, the very experiential aspect of learning that allows professional and academic goals to be achieved simultaneously. It is well known that about half of the costs of higher education are not directly related to education (housing, food, etc.). Online learning allows you to almost completely offset these costs and in addition, save money on tuition fees. Not surprisingly, student savings is one of the key arguments in favor of online education. Another important advantage is the flexibility of learning. A student can adjust the time of attending virtual classes, the number of courses to be taken, and in some cases, the start and end times of the course. People enrolled in online education programs are often employed, have families, and are older. Online learning is a way out for many who can, due to financial, family or

professional circumstances, afford one or less hours of study per day.

Given the fact that in a rapidly changing world, some professions are losing their meaning (for example, the profession of stenographers, which is not in demand on the labor market), while others appear in a few years and are in unprecedented demand (for example, mobile application developer), there is a growing need for retraining. This task is successfully realized with the help of online education. There are interesting examples of combining two breakthrough innovations - online education and competency-based approach. A living example of competency-based online education is West-Governors University. This university was established on the initiative of governors of 19 American states in 1997 and is one of the promising models of universities of the future, educating 50 thousand students. West-Governors University has completely abandoned such common concepts as academic calendar, grades, credits, dependence of learning progress on academic hours and other traditional components. Training is fully focused on competencies, accordingly, the student pays not for the number of credits received, but for access to materials for a certain period of time. Not surprisingly, the university is popular with the working population, which is able to complete their studies faster due to practical experience.

Despite the significant advantages of online education, it has a number of disadvantages. In particular, the social and educational component of the learning process in higher education is practically leveled. This is especially true for students of traditional age. The importance of socialization, camaraderie, friendship and teamwork, has been repeatedly proven by scientists. In addition, there is no direct contact with the instructor in the classroom. One of the features of online education, allows us to conclude that it is not for everyone. The fact is that online learning requires a high level of self-organization and motivation. The statistics on students who fail to complete online education is incomparably higher than in traditional universities. Realizing this, some universities offer applicants a special test to determine the likelihood of a student's successful completion based on their study habits, self-organization, time management ability, and other aspects. Such universities consider it their duty to warn the applicant about possible problems. Another disadvantage of online education is the difficulty in identifying individual gaps in students' knowledge. In addition, some students need more detailed explanation and the possibility to ask questions "in real time" and receive answers.

One of the most popular innovations in higher education has been Massive open online courses (MOOCs). These are essentially free online courses that are available to anyone anywhere in the world and are designed to educate an unlimited number of students. These courses have become such a popular phenomenon that "The New York Times" named 2012 "the year of the MOOC." Many people, from both inside and outside of education, predicted that MOOCs would cause a revolution in higher education. The very first massively popular course, put freely available in 2011 by Stanford University professors Sebastian Thorne

and Peter Norvig, enrolled 160,000 students, more than 20,000 of whom, successfully completed it. That is, the two professors have taught more people in a few months than all of their colleagues combined, over many years of teaching. In addition, the course was open to absolutely anyone who wanted to take it, attracting international students from 190 countries. This momentous event took place a little over many years ago, and since then, MOOCs have achieved unprecedented results.[6] The leaders of the massive online course movement are three companies: - "Coursera": trains over 10 million people worldwide, and offers over 800 courses from over a hundred partner universities. For a small amount of money, it offers a specialization (a program consisting of several courses); - "EdX": a non-profit organization founded by Harvard University and the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. The organization plans to create a platform for course creation by ordinary users. The total number of listeners - 1.65 million students and about 4000 courses; - "Udacity": specializes mainly in courses in the field of information technology and business. This organization also offers a "nanodiploma" in cooperation with AT&T, the largest communications company in the United States. Educates 1.8 million people. The demographics of the students at Mechanical Electrical and Plumbing (MEP) are interesting. Among the millions enrolled in the course, 40% are from developing countries. This shows one undoubted advantage of these courses - they are open to everyone who has access to the Internet. That is, any Ukrainian, regardless of his or her place of residence, has the opportunity to take courses at the leading international universities of the world if there is an Internet connection. The total number of MEP courses exceeds 1200 units and their number is constantly growing.

Why is it important for the management and administration of Ukrainian higher education to know about so-called "breakthrough innovations"? Some may note that they do not concern domestic universities. After all, Ukrainian Higher Education institutions (HEIs) provide domestic-oriented knowledge in the state language and close to the students' place of residence (especially when it comes to regional HEIs). Undoubtedly, contextualized knowledge is important, the availability of education in the native language is undeniable, and for a large number of both rural and urban population studying at a nearby higher education institution is the most convenient. However, there are several reasons for the interest in the phenomenon of breakthrough innovations. First, Ukraine is increasingly integrated into international educational processes. The Bologna process, academic mobility, increased autonomy, growing number of publications in foreign editions and partnerships with foreign universities, as well as other trends, make Ukrainian education more integrated into the global educational process. According to the widespread neo-institutional theory, isomorphism, or homogeneity, of higher education systems and organizations is growing.[8] An inevitable result of the integration process is, by striving through

imitation, changes in the regulatory framework as a result of political will (such as the introduction of a three-tier training system in accordance with the Bologna Process). Accordingly, it can be assumed that Ukrainian education will eventually become more and more similar to the education of other countries, and in general, this will lead to increased unification of international education. Thus, breakthrough innovations can have a very real impact on domestic universities. Firstly, Ukraine is actively introducing bilingualism at all levels of education. English today is the key to open almost any door to the global information space. It can be assumed that access to online education, open educational resources, and massive online MEP courses can seriously influence the decisions of the younger generation, which is well versed in computer technologies and fluent in English. Secondly, the boom in information technology has spared our country. The ubiquitous high-speed wireless and mobile Internet is the first priority for access to high-tech online education. The ability to use the Internet, participate in forums, collaborate on simple collaborative platforms, and use audio and video applications is the second key ingredient. Both of these aspects are already present and quite well developed. Thirdly, online resources seriously influence pedagogical practice. Many teachers and educators are faced with the fact that students can find information more mobile, which confuses some teachers and can undermine their authority as educators. Foreign researchers often argue that teachers' monopoly on knowledge is disappearing. A person no longer needs to keep detailed facts in his or her memory, which become available at the touch of a few keys. Printed textbooks do not reflect rapidly changing reality, and a traditional textbook can take years to develop, adapt, and implement. Electronic sources of information, on the other hand, are constantly being updated, and the cost of such updates is negligible. Canadian professor George Siemens even refers to the famous Google search engine as a part of students' brains that they can reliably access at any time. However, this fact by no means excludes the importance of the role of the teacher, today. On the contrary, with an unprecedented amount of unorganized information, students are faced with the challenge of selecting the right information and formulating a clear understanding of the problem. While information technology is bringing the factual erudition of the student to near maximum, the role of the teacher, on the other hand, is becoming more complex than before. From transmitting specific facts, the teacher moves to conveying an understanding of the underlying ideas and concepts, as well as creating an environment for active learning and application of knowledge.

This article considers the topical issues of modern innovations in higher education. Discussions on this topic continue and, apparently, the issue of breakthrough innovations will attract more and more attention. There is no doubt that awareness of existing innovations and their potential scope is vital for leaders of Ukrainian higher education.

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